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Site-specific production forecast through data-driven and engineering models

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Abstract. The present study investigates the predictive capabilities of two site-specific wind power forecasting models. The two approaches make use of a machine learning ensemble model that combines forecasts from several numerical weather predictions (NWP) to match local observations. In the first approach, the training data consists of historical site power production recordings. This yields a black-box model that includes the wind farm behaviour. The second approach is a combination of data-driven and explicit modelling. In the first step, the machine learning ensemble model forecasts the site wind conditions. Then, this input is fed to a site-specific engineering wake model. This hybrid "grey-box" approach explicitly resolves some farm flow effects.

The study shows that the performance of both methods differs over the wind speed range. The purely data-driven model performs better at medium wind speeds, which also occur more often. The hybrid method predictions agree better during periods of higher wind speeds. In the last part, the study showcases the capabilities of the forecasting methods when participating in the energy market. Additionally, the engineering wake model allows for power maximisation through wind farm control.

1. Introduction

Accurately forecasting the power output of wind farms is a key aspect for the future energy grid [1]. Firstly, asset production planning and thus grid stability depend on the estimated generation. Secondly, a reliable forecasting capability allows for additional coordination and optimisation of the individual assets, e.g. power tracking or battery storage control [2, 3]. The modelling challenge spans from the mesoscale with large weather phenomena down to the micro-climate at the site [1]. The individual power output per turbine is finally affected by local terrain flow and wake effects. The present work addresses the bridge from large to small spatial scales, called "terra incognita" [4]. Two distinct forecasting methods are evaluated and compared: one of them predicts the total power output of the plant over a time horizon, while the other one aims at predicting the contribution of each turbine as well. Both approaches address the problem by learning from on-site observations. The forecast horizon is 36 hours with 10 minute resolution. The choice of the forecast horizon is motivated by the application in the day-ahead market, where the bidding stage for the day-ahead stage (24-hour duration) closes 12 hours before the start of delivery. The investigated plant is a medium sized onshore wind farm. Finally, the paper presents a potential use case for the proposed forecast model. Through an

improved prediction capability, an accurate economic dispatch of the plant is possible. The study is organized as follows. First the general methodology and the farm case are outlined. The next section describes the adaptation of the specific models. Finally, the result section quantifies the predictive performance, while the application section showcases an economic dispatch scenario with a battery storage unit.

2. Study overview

Figure 1 reports the forecasting methodologies. The two investigated approaches are named "A: Direct Power Forecast" and "B: Hybrid Method". Generally, each method translates the regional forecast from a NWP model into a localised forecast. This is achieved through an offline training phase, which adapts the elements of both approaches to the specific site. Historical SCADA recordings from the investigated wind farm itself are used for this purpose.

The first element in both methods is a machine learning (ML) ensemble model consisting of multiple neural networks. The type of training data determines its output. Method A uses directly the aggregated turbine power production in the training phase, in the sense that the model will directly forecast the combined farm power. This makes this method a data-driven black-box approach, as the turbine response and flow effects (i.e. wakes, terrain-induced speedups, and other extra and intra-plant phenomena) are implicitly included.

Figure 1. Flow chart of the two investigated methodologies. Method A translates a weather forecast directly into a farm power forecast. Method B first predicts the site wind conditions which are then fed to an engineering flow model to obtain the turbine power. The training data from the SCADA system includes individual and aggregated power output P_T and P_{Farm} , site wind speed U_0 and site wind direction Γ_0 .

The hybrid method B consists of two elements. The first is similar to method A, however the training data consists of aggregated wind speed and direction measurements at the turbines. This way, the ML ensemble model is trained to predict the expected site wind conditions, i.e. wind speed and direction. In the second step, this output is fed to an engineering flow model. Contrary to method A, wake effects and turbine responses are explicitly modelled. To improve

the accuracy of the engineering model, it is also site-specifically adapted with the "wind farm as sensor" method [5].

2.1. Wind farm

The investigated site consists of 12×2.05 MW machines in an irregular layout. All turbines have a rotor diameter of $D = 82$ m and a hub height of 80 m. The terrain is composed of gently rolling hills and can be characterised as semi-complex. The farm is located on a slope that elevates towards the south-west direction. The turbine base heights vary from approximately 300 m to 360 m. The southernmost turbines are close to the crest of the hill. The ground roughness is characterised by grassland. The prevailing wind directions are in the south to west sector. Two years of high frequency 1 Hz data were available from 2019 to 2021. The preprocessing to flag irregular turbine operation and correct the yaw drive offsets is described in [6]. For the present case, the data was downsampled by averaging the SCADA channels to 10 min intervals.

Method A requires the total farm power P_{Farm} for the training phase. However, timestamps where all turbines are in regular operation are not very likely. In the present case, in only 29% of the timestamps, all of the 12 turbines reported regular data. Therefore, timestamps with up to 3 missing turbines were made available by replacing the unavailable turbine power with the farm average power. This way, 83% of the data could be used.

From the filtered data, we manually selected seven months to form a test set covering each season. The other 17 months were split into a training set (88%) and a validation set (12%). For this split we used blocks of 60 hours and shuffled these. The training and validation sets were used for both the ML ensemble model and the engineering flow model adaptation (section 3.2), here including the individual turbine power productions P_T . The test set was only used to compare the final methods A and B.

The hybrid method B requires the site inflow wind speed U_0 and wind direction Γ_0 . These conditions were synthesised from the turbine SCADA data. The wind direction was obtained as the farm circular mean of the nacelle positions. The wind speed was obtained by averaging the rotor-equivalent wind speed of the free stream turbines. Thus, the obtained site inflow can be considered a "virtual metmast", as it represents a site-mean inflow opposed to a metmast with a specific location.

3. Model adaptation

3.1. Machine learning ensemble model

The ML forecasting models for method A and B were developed and trained according to the same approach. Both use an ensemble method consisting of multiple Fully Connected Neural Networks (FCNNs). The training was based on a combination of historical measurements of wind speed, power, and deterministic predictions from two NWP models (ICON [7], ARPEGE [8]). The grid point used from the NWP model was less than one kilometre away from the wind farm centre.

Instead of training one FCNN for the full forecast horizon of 36 hours, 12 networks are trained each for a specific segment of the horizon. Since the first hours can be predicted with a higher accuracy than the last ones, the first segments cover a shorter horizon than the last ones. Figure 2 demonstrates which of the 12 FCNNs covers which forecast horizon segment. To obtain more robust results for each prediction step, an ensemble approach is applied as well, where n different models, i.e. ensemble members, cover the same prediction step. The choice of $n = 4$ offered a good compromise between robustness and training time reduction. The overlapping hours are combined by weighting the predictions. The middle point of each prediction is weighted the most, while the predictions from the first and last hours contribute the least to the merged prediction. In addition to the ensemble method, an automated feature selection algorithm is applied to each network to extract the most important weather forecast values and historical

Figure 2. Visualisation of the 36-hour forecast coverage by the 12 FCNNs. The orange section depicts a point on the forecast horizon (forecast minute 500). It shows an example of how the ensemble members are composed and weighted.

power or wind speed measurements. The optimal number of features depends, among other factors, on the forecast horizon. As a result, the number of features selected for each network ranges from 12 to 598.

The varying complexity of the forecast task and the different amount of input parameters necessitate a custom architecture and training of the FCNNs. An automated hyper-parameter optimisation algorithm [9] is thus applied after the feature selection. For each network, the number of neurons in the two hidden layers, the weight decay, and batch size were optimised. For the training, Adam [10] was used as optimiser and the mean squared error as a loss function.

3.2. Engineering flow model

The second element of the hybrid method B is the engineering flow model, which in this study is chosen to be the FLORIS [11] model. However, using it in its baseline configuration could limit the predictive accuracy of the hybrid approach. Therefore, the baseline model is site adapted following the "wind farm as sensor" approach, described in greater detail in [5]. Historical SCADA data is used to tune some of the model parameters, including the wake velocity deficit and the wake-added turbulence. Simultaneously, the same data is used to learn unmodelled flow phenomena, as those induced by the terrain, vegetation and the interaction of the farm with the atmospheric boundary layer.

Following ref. [5], the corrections are introduced based on the split between background and wake flow regime: the scalar wind speed field U at a reference height can be causally decomposed as

$$U(\mathbf{A}_0, Q) = U_0 \left(1 + \Delta\hat{U}\right) + \Delta U_{\text{wake}}, \quad (1)$$

where the functional dependency in the present study is made up of the site-average ambient conditions $\mathbf{A}_0 = [U_0, \Gamma_0]$ consisting of wind speed, wind direction, and secondly, of the spatial position Q . The second term on the right hand side, ΔU_{wake} , represents the velocity reduction

caused by wakes. The correction term in parenthesis on the right hand side represents an heterogeneous flow correction, normalised by the site-average wind speed $\Delta\hat{U} = \Delta U/U_0$. Whereas ΔU_{wake} is modelled by FLORIS, this term has the task of representing an heterogeneous background flow that includes the effects of terrain, vegetation and farm-boundary layer interactions.

The calibration of the wake part ΔU_{wake} , is introduced through tuning parameters p_k that are added to the model baseline parameters,

$$k = k_{\text{init}} + p_k, \quad (2)$$

where k represents a generic model parameter. The four standard parameters of the Gaussian wake model and the Crespo-Hernandez wake added turbulence model, respectively, were subject to re-calibration [12, 13].

The modelling of the heterogeneous background field correction ΔU is established through a grid of flow speed up nodes. The spatial heterogeneity over the farm area is discretised using a 2D mesh, where the value of the field at a generic point Q is obtained by interpolating a set of discrete nodal values \mathbf{p}_U through assumed shape functions $\mathbf{n}(\mathbf{A}_0, Q)$. The dependency on \mathbf{A}_0 indicates that the 2D spatial interpolation is expanded in additional dimensions to capture the influence of environmental conditions, namely wind direction and wind speed. The speed up at a specific location can then be written as

$$\Delta U(\mathbf{A}_0, Q) = \mathbf{n}^T(\mathbf{A}_0, Q) \mathbf{p}_U. \quad (3)$$

For the present case, the grid of tuning nodes consists of a rectangular grid of 5×4 nodes in the x - (east-west) and y - (south-north) directions, respectively. The spacing is 400 m in both directions. As stated, the heterogeneous correction is furthermore dependent on the site-average wind direction. A new set of nodes was placed every 30° of wind direction, starting from $\Gamma_0 = 0^\circ$. Additionally, the correction is dependent on wind speed. It was indeed observed that the model prediction error changed from under to over prediction from lower to higher inflow wind speeds. It was therefore concluded, that the flow is not Reynolds independent, but behaves differently at higher wind speeds [14]. The speed up node grid was further discretized into the wind speed dimension for speeds $U_0 = [5, 7, 9] \text{ ms}^{-1}$. This resulted in $5 \times 4 \times 12 \times 3 = 720$ speed up parameters. A different subset of the grid is shown in each panel of Figure 3 for the respective environmental conditions \mathbf{A}_0 .

All spatial correction and wake calibration parameters are stacked in an array of unknown parameters $\mathbf{p} = [\mathbf{p}_U^T, \mathbf{p}_w^T]$. Together, a \mathbf{p} -vector of 728 parameters needed to be identified. SCADA data is used to simultaneously learn the parameters that describe the correction field and to tune the ones of the engineering wake model. A maximum likelihood estimation finds the set of parameters that best describe the observed power output of the individual turbines. Note that this is a different target than the total farm power output, where positive and negative deviations cancel out. 4898 samples of 10 minute SCADA observations from the training data set were used for this task.

The panels of Figure 3 show the obtained relative background correction field $\Delta\hat{U}$ for two different directions and wind speed regimes. From the south-western direction, the flow first passes the sharp hillcrest and then follows a descending terrain elevation. While the correction field seems uniform for the low wind speed in panel 3a, it is highly heterogeneous for the higher wind speed 3c. While the front turbines near the crest are in a higher wind speed region, the rest of the farm experiences a 5-10% slow down. This could be due to a turbulent effect of the terrain ridge, where the flow is detached at higher wind speed. When the wind comes from the north-eastern direction (3b,c), it is confronted with an increasing elevation. Here the high and low wind speed correction fields show a higher similarity with the terrain elevation. It should be

Figure 3. Learned heterogeneous correction field for the combinations of wind directions $\Gamma_0 = [225, 45]$ and wind speeds $U_0 = [5, 9] \text{ ms}^{-1}$.

noted that no CFD or other source of information was available to verify the obtained results. However, due to the low turbine count, farm-boundary layer interactions have probably little influence. The simultaneous wake model parameter tuning resulted overall in a slightly slower wake decay, causing e.g. 1.3 % higher wake loss for $\Gamma_0 = 275^\circ$ and $U_0 = 8 \text{ ms}^{-1}$. The relative power prediction error of the augmented model is defined as $\hat{\epsilon}_T = (P_{T, \text{model}} - P_T) / P_{T, \text{rated}}$ for a single turbine. The aggregated r.m.s.-error is reduced by 23% from $\hat{\epsilon}_{T, \text{rms}} = 0.084$ to 0.065 for the test data set.

4. Results

4.1. Predictive performance

The following section evaluates the predictive performance for the direct power forecast A and the hybrid method B. To give an example, Figure 4 shows a forecast for an arbitrary point in time in the test data set. The figure reports the measured total farm power over the 36 hour forecast horizon. The farm output ramps up in the first third, then operates at full capacity and decreases to reach turbine stop in the last third. The forecasts of method A and B are made at the start of the period. Both methods capture the overall trend. A fluctuation on the scale of 2-3 h and 15 MW towards the end of the horizon is however not captured.

Next, the overall performance is evaluated throughout the test part of the data set. The prediction error is defined as

$$\hat{\epsilon} = \frac{P_{F, \text{model}} - P_F}{P_{F, \text{rated}}}, \quad (4)$$

normalised by the farm nameplate capacity. Figure 5a reports the r.m.s. of the two models

Figure 4. Example forecast over 36 hours.

Figure 5. (a) r.m.s.-error of the test dataset, binned by forecast hour. (b) r.m.s.-error of the 4 h predictions (circle), binned by measured wind speed.

binned over the entire prediction horizon. Both methods show an initial rapid error increase in the first 4 h to up $\hat{\epsilon}_{rms} = 0.13$. The error then increases at a lower rate to ca. $\hat{\epsilon}_{rms} = 0.16$ at 36 h. The performance trend of both methods is similar, although the purely data-driven method A shows consistently a slightly lower error. To highlight the effect of the FLORIS adaptation (cf. sec. 3.2), the figure additionally reports the result of the hybrid method with a baseline engineering model. In this case, the error increases by ca. 16 % over the entire range.

Figure 5b further discretises the performance of the two methods over the wind speed range. To this end, the error of all 4 h forecasts (circle in panel (a)) was binned in 2 ms^{-1} wide bins and again aggregated to r.m.s.-error. Over this dimension, the resulting trend for the two methods differs. For medium wind speeds, the direct power forecast performs better, while the situation is reversed for wind speeds above 12 ms^{-1} . The lack of accuracy of data-driven models in predicting the maximum, rated farm production is commonly observed and also visible in Figure 4. The hybrid method, on the other hand, performs better, because the saturated production at higher wind speeds is modelled through the power curves of the turbines. The higher probability of

wind speeds in the medium range (the site average wind speed is 8.3 ms^{-1}) explains the overall slightly better performance of the data-driven method in panel (a).

4.2. Application: Economic dispatch of the wind farm in combination with battery storage participating in the German energy market

This section showcases and evaluates the performance of the forecasting methods in a realistic application scenario. It considers the combination of the existing wind plant with a (in reality non-existing) battery storage unit, to form a wind-storage-based hybrid power plant (HPP) [15]. The scenario evaluates the participation of the HPP in the German energy market using the two different forecasting methods. Additionally, the second method B allows to optimise the farm through the deployment of a wind farm control algorithm, in the present case wake steering [16].

The site-adapted FLORIS model (as described in Sect. 3.2) models the wind farm. The assumed battery consists of a model of the electrical equivalent circuit of a 6 MW/6 MWh lithium-ion unit including electrical, thermal, and degradation, sub-models. A detailed description of the modelling approach can be found in [17]. The wind farm and battery are connected to the electricity grid through a single point of interconnection.

Access to the energy market is implemented through an energy management system (EMS) in a stage-wise manner. The HPP first participates in a day-ahead bidding stage, which is then followed by intra-day bid-revision stages. The EMS optimiser uses the wind power forecast from either method, a market price forecast, and the battery model with current state of charge. Through this, it calculates the total power that the HPP should generate over a time interval, as well as the share of the wind farm generation that maximises profit. The HPP revenue is estimated as a product of market price and respective power bids. The cost of battery damage is estimated and minimised directly using the parametric online rainflow counting approach [17]. The optimisation is subject to constraints to minimise deviations between the summed (pre-)bidding (for both the day-ahead and intra-day stages) and the operational set-point of the HPP. The inevitable short-term forecast errors are compensated, post-market-closure, using wind farm curtailment and/or battery reserves.

An HPP controller is considered to minimise deviations between power generation and the EMS optimal power reference. The controller is formulated on a rule-based policy that, depending on wind farm availability, decides to either curtail the wind farm or generate the available power. The remaining power goes as a reference to the battery, depending on the battery current state of charge, to ensure fulfilment of the HPP reference. As wind farm power tracking is of key importance to maximise performance, the implementation is based on a tracking margin-boosting wind farm active power controller, which reduces the occurrence of saturation events of individual turbines [2].

Figure 6 shows the economic performance of the HPP. The net economic profit (shown in green) is calculated as the difference between revenue, cost, and penalty. Revenue (shown in blue) is calculated as the product of power bids and respective actual prices for both the day-ahead and intra-day markets. Cost (shown in red) is calculated as the fraction of the replacement cost of the battery due to the accumulated cyclic degradation. Penalty (shown in black) is calculated as the product of HPP generation error and balancing energy (*reBAP*) price. The first subplot shows the results when the data-driven approach is used to obtain the direct forecast of the wind power (method A). The second subplot shows the results for the hybrid forecasting approach (method B). Additionally, a yaw-offset-based wind farm control is implemented that aims to maximise wind farm power production by steering the wake away from the turbines. The offline control schedule was derived through the FLORIS own functionality using the site-adapted model [18]. It should be noted that the wind farm control implementation is possible in method B, where the forecaster has access to the inflow conditions at individual turbines within the farm. The case is named "C: Hybrid method + Maximum Power Wind Farm Control" and is

Figure 6. Economic performance of the HPP participation in energy market.

Figure 7. Dynamic performance of the HPP participation in energy market.

shown in the third subplot. Figure 7 shows the corresponding HPP power bid, generation, and battery usage for the three forecasting approaches.

For the considered simulation period of one day, the direct power forecasting method (A) results in a slightly higher bid and consequently higher revenue than the hybrid forecasting method (B). Owing to the forecast error, method A suffers smaller penalties for deviations, calculated using *reBAP* prices. However, in both methods, the battery energy is used to a similar extent to compensate for the forecast error, resulting in a very slight difference between the accumulated cost of battery damage. This is also evident from the battery state of charge (SOC) profile, where method A is characterised by frequent cycles of shorter depth, whereas method B has slow varying cycles of slightly larger depth. As a consequence, method A results in a 2.4% higher net profit than method B. As expected, method C bids more power in the market due to the effective deployment of wake-steering control. This in turn leads to higher revenue and the highest profit (8% more than method A), even though there is an increase in deviation penalty due to restricted battery usage because of SOC limits.

5. Conclusions

The presented study showcases two distinct methods for site-specific wind power forecasting. The first model was directly trained on farm power production and presents therefore a black box approach. The second model consisted of a site-specific wind condition forecast coupled with an adapted engineering model. Results indicate that the overall performance of both methods is comparable. The straightforward black-box method proved capable of dealing with the complex terrain and non-linear wake interactions of the farm, although some degradation in its accuracy occurred in the full-power regime. On the other hand, the hybrid method offers advantages when individual turbine output and conditions are of interest. This is indeed the case in various situations, for example for wind farm control, for operational optimisation, and for the provision of some grid services.

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